

HASTRICT on a page (or two) v1.2

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Introduction

HASTRICT are a set of high-level principles, designed to inform the development of approaches or plans for evaluating AI technologies, for use in GLAM organisations and the HASS disciplines.

The HASTRICT principles provide a starting point for practitioners to develop contextually appropriate and holistic evaluations of AI technologies. HASTRICT focuses on defining the specific use case and AI system components that will be subject to evaluation, and then on defining the particular people, measures, and processes that will be used to conduct an evaluation. In doing so, HASTRICT helps surface inevitable trade-offs in evaluation design.

Version history

This version (1.2) of the principles incorporates an additional principle (Accountable), resulting in the acronym extending from H-STRICK to HASTRICT. *Accountable* was added as a principle after discussions and feedback gathered during the AIINFRA Spring Workshop (2025), which was hosted at Australian National University, and brought together practitioners and researchers from Australia's cultural sector.

The HASTRICT principles

Principle	Definition	Pragmatic considerations
Human	The values, ethics, and standards applied during the evaluation of an AI system should reflect the expectations and commitments of the humans who will develop, use, interact with, and be impacted by the AI system.	Attempting to identify and define shared values is a complex, problematic task at the best of times. One option is to instead look to the values already embedded in the social settings where the AI system was developed and where it will be deployed. For the cultural and research sectors, FAIR and CARE principles are important starting points.

Accountable	Responsibility for the design of the evaluation, any deployment decisions resulting from the evaluation, and for ensuring alignment between evaluation practices and organisational policies and procedures is supported by clear lines of authority, with transparent documentation practices and mechanisms in place for auditing and overseeing AI evaluations and decisions.	Most organisations will already have established processes for technology procurement decisions. While AI evaluations tend to extend beyond the scope of these processes (e.g. due to the distinct ethical risks associated with AI technologies), existing technology procurement processes can be used as a starting point.
System targets	When conceptualising how to evaluate an AI system, the scope of the evaluation should extend -- i.e. target -- to the full breadth of sociotechnical components implicated in an AI system, rather than only to the AI models themselves.	Unless working within an entirely open-source paradigm, it is unlikely that evaluators will have access to all components of an AI system. Evaluation is still possible, but issues of transparency, reproducibility, and reliability will need to be considered.
Transparent	The various points of calibration for the system target (e.g. model settings, interface settings) should be transparently recorded during an evaluation and exposed to evaluation participants.	Depending on the AI use case, privacy or cultural safety concerns may merit selective opacity. Similarly, if using commercial AI, opacity may be enforced by the product design.
Reproducible	The probabilistic process by which AI models produce outputs, coupled with the unpredictable ways these outputs may interact with other system components, needs to be accounted for during evaluation.	Use individual interactions with an AI system to inform evaluation design and to identify potential problems with an AI system, but do not rely on individual interactions as the sole means of evaluation. Validate problems through large-scale automated testing.
Iterative	AI systems should be treated as dynamic, with an expectation of changing performance over time. Accordingly, evaluation approaches should be iterative, focused on establishing baselines and then monitoring performance over time.	Consider how to design a repeatable evaluation process, that can be iteratively applied to new versions of an AI system or model.
Contextually Informed	AI systems ought to be designed and deployed in ways that account for local context. A primary goal of an AI	To incorporate local context into an AI evaluation, the relevant local norms or standards must be translated into a baseline evaluation dataset and evaluation measures.

Measures & Baselines	evaluation is to determine alignment between an AI system and its deployment context.	Consider reviewing existing measures for key ethical concepts (e.g. fairness, equity), and selecting the measure that best aligns with local norms and the use case.
Tasks, workflows & use cases	Although AI systems are frequently marketed as general purpose tools, evaluations need to be undertaken at the level of specific tasks, workflows, and use cases, as good performance in one domain or use case should not be assumed to be predictive of good performance in another.	Not all tasks or use cases are equal. Rather than seeking to evaluate AI systems for use across an entire sector or organisation, it may be more tractable to identify high risk or priority use cases, which merit bespoke evaluations, and to then provide support to individual users to make informed AI decisions regarding low risk or lower priority use cases.